

of the amido nitrogen atom. However, disappearance and lowering of NCS bend frequencies occurring at 1180 cm^{-1} and 1140 cm^{-1} to 1110 cm^{-1} in Cu(II), and at 1160 cm^{-1} and 1110 cm^{-1} in the case of Hg(II) and Pb(II) complexes, indicated the participation of nitrogen atom (attached to amido nitrogen) in bond formation.

The new bands appearing at 460 cm^{-1} , 398 cm^{-1} and at 480 cm^{-1} in the spectra of Cu(II), Hg(II) and Pb(II) complexes respectively were attributed to M-N (metal-nitrogen) stretching frequencies. Further two bands appearing at 330 cm^{-1} and 296 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of Hg-complex and at 340 cm^{-1} and 310 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of Pb(II) complex were assignable to Hg-S and Pb-S stretching frequencies respectively. However, in case of Cu(II) complex very weak M-S absorption bands were observed in the spectrum of copper complex and, therefore, its exact assignment became difficult. The following structure was assigned to these complexes

References

1. C. I. D. ZARAFONETIS and J. P. KALAS, *Proc. Soc. Exptl. Biol. Med.*, 1969, 105, 560.
2. B. L. FREDLANDER and A. FRUST, *Proc. Soc. Exptl. Biol. Med.*, 1952, 81, 638.
3. H. W. CAUSMAN, C. L. RHYKERD, H. R. HINDERLITER, K. S. SOTT and L. F. AUDRIETH, *Bot. Gaz.*, 1953, 144, 292.
4. T. W. COMBELL, V. S. FOLDI and J. FARAGO, *J. Appl. Polymer Soc.*, 1959, 2, 155.
5. M. J. CAMPBELL and R. GRZESKOWIAK, *J. Chem. Soc. A.*, 1967, 3, 401.
6. AJAYI, O. SUNDAY, GODDARD and DANIDK, *J. Chem. Soc. Dalton Trans.*, 1973, 17, 1754.
7. D. R. GODDARD, B. D. LODAM, AJAI, O. SUNDAY and M. J. CAMPBELL, *J. Chem. Soc. A.*, 1969, 3, 512.
8. R. S. VERMA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1966, 43, 558.
9. G. R. BURNS, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1968, 7, 277.
10. L. J. BELLAMY and P. E. ROGASCH, *J. Chem. Soc. London*, 1960, 2218.
11. I. SUZUKI, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1962, 35, 1286, 1449, 1456.
12. K. SWAMINATHAN and H. M. NH, IRWING, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1964, 26, 1291.

Schiff Bases as Chelating Agents for Nickel (II)

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TWO types of ligands were prepared and identified as reported earlier¹⁻³. Their general structural formulae are as follows :

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Isolation of Nickel (II) complexes :

On mixing ethanolic solutions of nickel chloride hexahydrate (A.R.) and the corresponding ligands in stoichiometric ratio (1:2) different coloured solutions resulted in separate experiments. The reaction mixture was evaporated nearly on water bath ; methanol (10 ml) was added to it and was left at room temperature for slow evaporation. The coloured crystalline compounds separated out ; which were filtered off, washed with ethanol and then dried in a vacuum desiccator over fused calcium chloride.

General Structures of Schiff Bases :

where,

R=4-Acenaphthyl,

4-methyl-7-hydroxy-8-acetocoumaryl,

4-methylphenyl.

R'=2-Carboxylicphenyl, 2-hydroxyphenyl.

Physico-Chemical Measurements and Instruments Used :

The electronic diffuse reflectance spectra were taken in a Ziess PMQ II spectrophotometer with a reflectance attachment RA₈. Electronic spectra in specpure solvents were recorded in a Hilger UVISPEK spectrophotometer using 1 cm cell. Magnetic susceptibility, molar conductance and I. R. spectral studies of the compounds have been made as reported earlier¹⁻³. Elemental analysis of the compounds was made at C.D.R.I., Lucknow. Acidic complexes in aqueous and DMSO medium show comparable molar conductance values.

Results and Discussions

All the complexes are soluble in DMF, DMSO, NM and benzene. The molar conductance (λ_M) values indicate their electrolytic as well as nonelectrolytic nature⁴.

The room temperature magnetic moments of all the complexes (Table 1) fall within the range 2.83-3.45 B. M. expected for octahedral spin free Ni(II) complexes⁵.

The diffuse reflectance spectra of the present Ni(II) complexes are characterised by three main bands as shown in Table 2 which are in close agreement to those predicted from Ballhausen and Liehr⁶ energy level diagram for Ni(II) ions in O_h symmetry. The results are more or less in good agreement with those reported

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA AND OTHER PROPERTIES OF THE COMPLEXES

Complex	Colour	% Elemental analysis			μ_{eff} in B.M. (303°K)	λ_M Ohm ⁻¹ mole ⁻¹ cm ² DMSO (Aqueous)
		N Calcd. (Found)	C Calcd. (Found)	Ni Calcd. (Found)		
H ₂ [Ni(C ₂₁ H ₁₆ NO ₄) ₂ Cl ₂]	Pale blue	3.68 (3.60)	66.31 (65.80)	7.76 (7.58)	3.06	210 (190)
[Ni(C ₂₀ H ₁₄ NO ₄) ₂]	Blue ^a	4.24 (4.14)	72.84 (72.06)	8.95 (8.82)	3.14	28
H ₂ [Ni(C ₁₉ H ₁₃ NO ₄) ₂]	Blue	3.83 (3.75)	62.40 (61.99)	8.33 (8.48)	3.02	175 (160)
H ₂ [Ni(C ₁₈ H ₁₂ NO ₄) ₂]	Green blue	4.15 (4.14)	64.02 (63.54)	8.70 (8.62)	2.98	198 (175)
[Ni(C ₁₆ H ₁₂ NO ₄) ₂]	Pale blue	4.74 (4.68)	65.00 (64.38)	9.93 (9.85)	3.11	35
[Ni(C ₁₅ H ₁₁ NO ₄) ₂]	Yellow, green	5.20 (5.14)	67.07 (66.82)	10.93 (11.01)	3.17	40

TABLE 2—PRINCIPAL BAND POSITIONS IN THE REFLECTANCE SPECTRA WITH PROBABLE ASSIGNMENTS AND THE LIGAND FIELD PARAMETERS

Complex	Band positions (cm ⁻¹) and their assignments			Splitting energy 10D _q (cm ⁻¹)	Racah Parameter B (cm ⁻¹)	B	ν_2 Calcd. (cm ⁻¹)	ν_3 Calcd. (cm ⁻¹)	ν_3/ν_1
	$^3A_{2g}(F)$	$^3T_{2g}(F)$	$^3T_{1g}(F)$						
H ₂ [(C ₂₁ H ₁₆ NO ₄) ₂ Cl ₂]	9,800	15,610	25,800	9,800	800	0.74	15,760	25,517	1.59
[Ni(C ₂₀ H ₁₄ NO ₄) ₂]	10,800	17,000	26,000	10,800	707	0.65	16,700	26,300	1.57
H ₂ [Ni(C ₁₉ H ₁₃ NO ₄) ₂]	10,500	16,600	26,000	10,500	740	0.69	16,415	26,140	1.58
[Ni(C ₁₆ H ₁₂ NO ₄) ₂]	10,800	16,800	26,000	10,800	693	0.64	16,700	26,050	1.55
[Ni(C ₁₅ H ₁₁ NO ₄) ₂]	10,400	16,900	29,130	10,400	989	0.91	16,020	28,780	1.62
H ₂ [Ni(C ₁₉ H ₁₃ NO ₄) ₂]	10,100	16,800	25,400	10,100	793	0.73	16,120	26,100	1.66

for octahedral Ni(II) complexes⁷⁻⁸. Although the diffuse reflectance and solvent spectra of the complexes are similar but the former shows three insignificant extra shoulders at about 6000 cm⁻¹, 7000 cm⁻¹ and 13000 cm⁻¹. These can be due to ligand overtones, some lowering in symmetry⁹ and spin forbidden transitions $^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow ^1E_g(D)$ as suggested by Jorgensen¹⁰.

I. R. Spectra :

A comparison of i.r. spectra of the ligands with those of Ni(II) complexes indicates lowering of stretching frequency due to azomethine (=C=N- or -CH=N-) group as ~1600 to ~1580 cm⁻¹. This shifting of frequencies suggests the formation of metal nitrogen bond which is further confirmed by the appearance of bands¹¹ at ~500 cm⁻¹. Anthranilic acido ligands

exhibit bands¹² at ~2700 cm⁻¹ due to -OH of carboxylic group, however, these bands are shifted in the complexes due to deprotonation.

Phenolato ligands consist of stretching frequency due to $\nu(OH)$ at ~3400 cm⁻¹, however, these frequencies are also shifted because of complexation with Ni(II). Thus the formation of metal-oxygen (M-O) bonds¹³ occurs which is confirmed by the appearance of bands at ~400 cm⁻¹. The acyl ligands show bands at ~1700 cm⁻¹ due to acyl group, however, these stretching frequencies are lowered in the complexes due to chelation through oxygen of ketonic group.

References

1. P. SINGH, V. SINGH, B. P. SINGH and R. P. MAHESH, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1975, 13, 734.

NOTES

2. H. A. MOHANTA and K. C. DASH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, 54, 166.
3. P. SINGH, G. P. POKHARIYAL and V. SINGH, *Acta Chim.* (Budapest) Accepted.
4. S. P. GHOSH and P. BHATTACHARJEE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, 51, 308.
5. F. A. COTTON and G. WILKINSON, "Advanced Inorganic Chemistry", Interscience Publication Inc., N. Y., 1962, p. 738.
6. A. D. LIEHR and C. J. BALLHAUSEN, *Ann. Phys.*, 1959, 6, 134.
7. K. C. PATEL and D. E. GOLDBERG, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1972, 34, 637.
8. M. P. TEOTIA, D. K. RASTOGI and W. U. MALIK, *Inorg. Chimica Acta*, 1973, 7, 340.
9. R. WALTON, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1966, 28, 2229.
10. C. K. JORGENSEN, *Acta Chem. Scand*, 1955, 9, 1362.
11. M. P. TEOTIA, D. K. RASTOGI and W. U. MALIK, *Inorg. Chimica Acta*, 1973, 7, 343.
12. D. D. OZHA, K. N. KAUL and S. MEHTA, *Curr. Sci.*, 1974, 43, 344.
13. P. SINGH, V. SINGH, R. L. GOEL, B. P. SINGH and R. P. MAHESH, *Curr. Sci.*, 1976, 45, 137.

2-Hydroxy-4-Methylpropiophenone oxime as an Analytical Reagent : Studies on Nickel Complex

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THE well known reagents for gravimetric determination of nickel are dimethylglyoxime¹, nioxime², resacetophenone oxime³. 2-Hydroxy-5-methylpropiophenone oxime⁴, 2-hydroxy-4-methylacetophenone oxime⁵ and 5-ethylresacetophenone oxime⁶ have been used as analytical reagents for nickel. In a project designed to develop new organic reagents for the determination of metal ions the use of 2-hydroxy-4-methylpropiophenone oxime has been investigated as a gravimetric reagent for Ni(II). An ethanolic solution of the reagent reacts with Ni(II) quantitatively forming a green complex of 1:2 stoichiometry analysing for Ni(C₁₀H₁₂O₂N)₂. The Ni(II) complex is insoluble in hot water and hot aq. ethanol (60–70% v/v). The complex can be dried without decomposition at 110–20° and is directly weighable as Ni(C₁₀H₁₂O₂N)₂. Cations like aluminium(III), cadmium(II), lead(II), zinc(II), mercury(II), barium(II), calcium(II), manganese(II), cobalt(II), magnesium(II) and anions like

tartrate, citrate, chloride, nitrate are found not to interfere at pH range 5.0 to 5.5. Interference of Fe(III) was removed by masking with sodium potassium tartrate before adding the reagent. Gravimetric determination of copper and nickel in their binary mixture has been carried out with satisfactory results taking advantage of the different pH range for precipitation.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A. R. grade. Stock solutions of metal ions were prepared by dissolving pure salts in double distilled water and were employed after standardisation by standard methods.

Ammonium hydroxide and acetic acid were used to prepare buffers of different pH values.

Reagent : 2-Hydroxy-4-methylpropiophenone Oxime :

2-Hydroxy-4-methylpropiophenone⁷ was obtained in almost quantitative yield by Fries migration of m-cresyl propionate⁸ in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride. Its oxime⁷ was prepared by refluxing its alcoholic solution with hydroxylamine hydrochloride and potassium hydroxide (40%). It was purified by repeated crystallisation from petroleum, m.p. 104°.

Gravimetric estimation of Ni(II) : An aliquot of standard solution of Ni(II) containing 6 to 20 mg of Ni(II) was diluted to 150 ml and pH was adjusted to 5.5 using ammonia and acetic acid buffer. The contents were heated to 60–70° and treated with 1% ethanolic solution of 2-hydroxy-4-methylpropiophenone oxime added dropwise with constant stirring (about twice the theoretical amount). The green precipitate obtained was digested on a water-bath for 30 min and filtered through a G-4 sintered glass crucible. It was washed with hot water several times and finally with 60% ethanol and dried at 110–20° to a constant weight. It has been found that the precipitation of nickel is quantitative in the pH range 5.0–10.0. The conversion factor (nickel/nickel complex) is 0.1416. Some representative results are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF Ni(II)

Ni(II) taken (mg)	Ni(II) found (mg)	Error (%)
5.94	5.92	-0.34
11.88	11.85 11.82	-0.25 -0.51
14.85	14.87 14.85	+0.13 ±0.00
20.79	20.81 20.85	+0.096 +0.29
29.70	29.8	+0.34

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